

Case Report: Early Onset Infection Following No-Scalpel Vasectomy

Dr Geoff Cashion, BBus MBBS FACRRM FRCEM, Lead Vasectomist, Vasectomy Australia. Sydney, Australia.

Abstract

We report a case of early onset infection following a no-scalpel vasectomy in a 31-year-old male. The patient presented with symptoms of swelling, redness, and pain on the third day post-procedure. Initial telehealth assessment and ultrasound indicated cellulitis with a small fluid collection. Despite oral antibiotics, the patient's condition worsened, requiring IV antibiotics and further management. This case highlights the potential for early presentation of infection following vasectomy, contrary to the common belief that infections typically manifest later.

Introduction

Vasectomy is a common and generally safe procedure for male sterilization.¹ The no-scalpel vasectomy (NSV) technique, introduced in the 1980s, has reduced complications such as bleeding and infection.² However, infections, although rare, remain a potential risk. It is generally believed that post-vasectomy infections present around day 5-7 post-operation. This case illustrates an atypical early onset of infection presenting on day 3 post-vasectomy.

Case Presentation

A 31-year-old male with no significant medical history presented for a routine no-scalpel vasectomy under local anesthesia. The procedure was uneventful, involving a single central keyhole incision and separation of the vasa using electrocautery and fascial interposition with a hemoclip on each side.

Day 3 Post-Procedure:

The patient reported swelling, redness, and pain on the left side of the scrotum. He also experienced chills the previous night. Telehealth assessment and a photograph (Figure 1) showed some redness without severe swelling. He was prescribed oral Bactrim DS 1bd and an ultrasound was ordered.

Figure 1 - Photo of scrotum Day 3 Post Procedure

Day 5 Post-Procedure:

The patient contacted the surgeon again, reporting worsening symptoms including increased swelling, erythema, and continued fevers and chills. A second photograph (Figure 2) showed significant worsening. The ultrasound indicated left scrotal wall thickening with a small fluid collection suggestive of cellulitis or a small hematoma. The patient was referred to the emergency department.

Figure 2 - Photo of scrotum Day 5 Post Procedure

Emergency Department Visit:

The patient was administered 2g of IV Cefazolin. Blood tests showed a CRP of 60 and a White Cell Count of 10.7. The urology team reviewed the photographs and discharged the patient with oral Cephalexin 500mg qid.

Day 6 Post-Procedure:

A follow-up ultrasound revealed marked thickening of the scrotal wall with increased vascularity and a small fluid collection adjacent to the epididymal head, indicating unresolved hematoma or potential abscess. The patient continued oral antibiotics .

Day 10 Post-Procedure:

The patient reported near full recovery with resolution of symptoms. He completed a course of Flucloxacillin 500mg qid.

Discussion

Infection following vasectomy, though rare, is a significant complication . This case demonstrates an atypically early presentation of infection at day 3 post-vasectomy. Early signs included erythema, pain, and systemic symptoms like chills, which prompted prompt antibiotic treatment .

Risk Factors and Management:

- Early identification and treatment of post-vasectomy infection are crucial .
- Patients should be educated on early signs of infection.
- Telehealth can be a useful tool for initial assessment and follow-up.
- Empirical use of broad-spectrum antibiotics is warranted in suspected cases .
- Ultrasound is a valuable diagnostic tool to assess for hematomas or abscess formation .

Conclusion:

This case underscores the importance of considering early onset infection in patients presenting with symptoms shortly after vasectomy. Prompt intervention and appropriate management are key to preventing severe complications. Further studies are needed to understand the factors contributing to early infection and to develop protocols for early detection and treatment.

Figures

- Figure 1: Scrotum on Day 3 post-vasectomy showing redness and mild swelling.
- Figure 2: Scrotum on Day 5 post-vasectomy showing significant swelling and erythema.

References

1. Yang F, Li J, Dong L, Tan K, Huang X, Zhang P, Liu X, Chang D, Yu X. Review of Vasectomy Complications and Safety Concerns. World J Mens Health. 2021 Jul;39(3):406-418. doi: [10.5534/wjmh.200073](https://doi.org/10.5534/wjmh.200073) Epub 2020 Jul 30. PMID: 32777870; PMCID: PMC8255399.
2. Cook LA, Pun A, Gallo MF, Lopez LM, Van Vliet HAAM. Scalpel versus no-scalpel incision for vasectomy. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews 2014, Issue 3.

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